

FEATURES OF TRANSLATION OF GERMAN PHRASEOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the author conducts a detailed analysis of such a common means of expression as a phraseological unit. Such grammatical and lexical constructions play a significant role in the semantic structure of the text. Phraseological units are especially difficult in the process of translating texts from a wide variety of fields of knowledge. After all, it is phraseological units that give the text its stylistic uniqueness. In this paper, the study is based on German phraseological units.

Today, scientific interest in the subject of phraseological units and the problems of their translation from one language to another has grown significantly. This is due not only to the general increase in the number of uses of phraseological units in texts on various topics, but also to the increasingly complex translation process. Phraseological units themselves create special difficulties in translation, since they carry the national and cultural properties of the language and people. Phraseological units not only convey information, but also affect the emotional and sensory aspects of a person, which is why they are especially common in texts in the artistic and advertising spheres. Preserving this effect during translation is the most important task of a translator.

In scientific literature, phraseological units are defined as lexical units that structurally represent predicative combinations of words and sentences [1]. Interest in the study of phraseological units in various scientific fields is associated with their uniqueness in each language and culture. Of particular importance in theoretical and practical work is the study of interlingual phraseological correspondences, their search and definition. It is within the framework of the translation process that scientists are most interested in the study of interlingual phraseological correspondences.

According to various scholars, when translating phraseological units, special attention should be paid to such characteristics as the degree of semantic fusion or separateness of the elements of the phraseological unit, the degree of clarity or ambiguity of the motivation, as well as stylistic coloring. Some characteristics of phraseological units are also distinguished, due to which their translation may be complicated, for example, separate design, national specificity, minor differences from ordinary words, weak connection between components, etc. [2]. It should be noted that the translation of phraseological units means not only the transfer of the semantic meaning of the language unit, but also the preservation of connotative characteristics.

Three types of correspondences to figurative phraseological units of the original are distinguished. The first of them is phraseological equivalents, in which the figurative phraseological unit coincides in all respects with the phraseological unit of the original. But such exact equivalents are rare and, among other things, may turn out to be the translator's "false friends", that is, have similarities with the original in form, but not in content. There are also phraseological analogues, that is, phraseological units with the same figurative meaning of the original, but with a different figurative component. The third is a tracing of a foreign-language figurative unit. With this type of correspondence, the image of the original is preserved [3].

In another typology of interlingual equivalence of phraseological units, full equivalents, partial, phraseological analogs and non-equivalent phraseological units are distinguished. Full equivalents practically coincide semantically and lexically with the phraseological unit in the original language. At the same time, morphologically, some differences may be present. For example, "von Kopf bis Fuß" - "from head to toe"; "in die Hand nehmen" - "to take into one's own hands"; "an der Nase herumführen" - "to lead by the nose". Partial equivalents are close to phraseological units of the original language in terms of semantics, but differ in the context of vocabulary and syntax. As researchers note: "a partial equivalence relationship occurs when, with semantic similarity, the compared idioms are also characterized by significant (but not complete) similarity in their component composition and syntactic structure, and the similarity clearly dominates over the differences" [4]. For example, "im Auge behalten" - "keep in sight"; "auf die Nerven gehen" - "get on your nerves"; "auf der Hand liegen" - "lie on the surface".

Phraseological analogues in this typology are idioms of the source language and the target language with similar actual meanings, but different internal forms. Semantic similarity is present, but formal similarity in the form of syntactic and component composition is absent.

For example: "sich in den Kopf setzen" - "to get it into your head" and "auf eigene Faust" - "at your own risk". Phraseological units without equivalents are used in cases where there are no phraseological equivalents in the target language. For example, the expression "nicht übers Herz bringen können" can only be translated into Russian through a description using a free combination of words - "not to be able to force yourself". Other examples include "ins Auge fassen" - "to outline, to plan" and "auf die Beine stellen" - "to set up" (work). In these examples, the essence of the complexity of the translation lies not only in choosing an equivalent, but also in the correct transmission of the semantic content, since the literal translation of these phraseological units does not correspond to the semantics of the phraseological unit in the original language.

Thus, the translation of phraseological units is especially difficult for a translator. The existing difficulties are related to the need to correctly select an equivalent for a phraseological unit and preserve the effect that the phraseological unit creates in the original language. Correspondences of phraseological units are divided according to the criterion of the degree of identity to the phraseological unit in the original language. In German, phraseological units are used in texts from a wide variety of areas of public life, which indicates their importance in the translation process. For a competent translation of a phraseological unit and preservation of its impact, it is extremely important that the translator has sufficient knowledge and translation competencies.

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